

Assisting Stakeholder Decision Making using System Dynamics Group Model Building

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Abstract

Stakeholder involvement in environmental management in Australia is increasingly participatory. A community-government partnership has been the central focus of the NSW program of water reforms since the inception of the *Water Act 2000*. Under the Act, it is the joint responsibility of the New South Wales Government and stakeholder-based Water Management Committees to develop Water Sharing Plans. Water Management Committees typically comprise government, environmental and agricultural representatives. This paper describes a System Dynamics group model-building workshop conducted with the Northern Rivers Water Management Committee. A role of the Committee was to determine the allocation of water between the water users and the environment. In order to achieve this goal, the Committee was provided with hydrological model outputs and other data by the NSW Government, however the decision support framework did not allow the incorporation of existing stakeholder knowledge and understanding. A group model-building workshop was convened to redress this problem. Participants found that the group model-building process was inclusive, enabled the exploration of different understanding, and incorporation of different knowledge-bases. Participants also found the approach allowed a holistic view of the water management system to be developed and assisted participants to understand the inherent complexities. Participants also commented that the group model-building experience assisted in a better understanding of the model development process. The models generated from the workshop and the response from participants suggest that there is potential for broader application of System Dynamics group model building to facilitate stakeholder involvement in environmental management policy and decision making.

Media summary

Group model building is demonstrated to be a promising approach for involving stakeholders in environmental management decision making.

Keywords

System Dynamics, group model building, stakeholder decision-making, water allocation, Northern NSW.

Introduction

Since 1994, States and Territories in Australia have been reviewing their water policies to meet the national Coalition of Australian Governments (COAG) Water Reform Framework. The COAG recognised that, in order to redress the widespread degradation of water resources, a package of measures was required to encompass the economic, environmental and social implications of water usage. The reforms proposed covered all aspects of the water industry, including institutional arrangements for regulation, management and service provision, water allocations and entitlements, water pricing, environmental protection, and emphasise the need for community input into decision making (Cullen 2000).

In New South Wales (NSW), in common with many other states of Australia, there has been a general evolution in all areas of natural resource management, from regulatory administration to outcomes-based legislation and a more participatory approach (Kerin 2000). A community-government partnership has been the central focus of the NSW program of water reforms. Under the *NSW Water Act 2000* it is the joint responsibility of the State Government and Water Management Committees to develop Water Sharing Plans. These Water Sharing Plans set in place rules for water use on a catchment scale for instance:

- (i) determining the proportion of flow available for extraction of surface water,
- (ii) recommending preferred drought management options, and
- (iii) developing local water trading rules.

In order to develop such Water Sharing Plans each Water Management Committee requires a considerable amount of knowledge and understanding of numerous catchment systems. For stakeholder government partnerships, such as Water Management Committees, to succeed in fulfilling their roles, there needs to be good communication between stakeholders, a holistic view (systems thinking), and an adaptive and interactive approach to decision making and decision support (den Exter, 2003).

The current decision support approach used by the NSW Department of Infrastructure Planning and Natural Resources (formerly the Department of Land and Water Conservation) for preparing Water Sharing Plans in unregulated surface water systems is the 'Integrated Quantity and Quality Modelling' (IQQM) framework. The IQQM framework provides stakeholders with a range of information on which to base their decisions. However, because of the technical nature of the modelling, and the number of Water Sharing Plans being prepared, stakeholders are limited to the number of scenarios they can request. Further, it is difficult to introduce new parameters to the IQQM framework, resulting in a lack of input to the model from water management stakeholders. This paper demonstrates the potential of System Dynamics modelling to address such shortcomings.

System Dynamics

System Dynamics has evolved from the combination of two divergent systems approaches—engineering systems, and management decision-making systems (Forrester 1960). According to the assumptions of System Dynamics:

- ∞ things are interconnected in complex patterns;
- ∞ the world is made up of rates, levels and feedback loops;
- ∞ information flows are intrinsically different from physical flows;
- ∞ non-linearities and delays are important elements in systems; and
- ∞ system behaviour arises out of system structure (Meadows 1989, Lane and Oliva 1998).

System Dynamics modelling interventions are commonly applied to management situations that require preliminary work to understand the nature of the problem. Building System Dynamics models assists in developing hypotheses, determining timeframes (commonly referred to as the 'reference mode') and determining the availability of historical data. Key variables are described (parameterisation), in the formulation phase, and the model begins to take form in detailed structure.

System Dynamics group model building

System Dynamics group model building is a result of the evolution of the application of System Dynamics modelling. The process of modelling has changed to facilitate greater stakeholder/client involvement where the modeller has increasingly taken the role of strategic counsellor and change agent (Weil 1980). This process has resulted, to a large extent, from practical considerations: without 'client' involvement at various stages throughout the process, models may be useful for the modeller, can easily lose wider relevance, and are unlikely to be taken up by others.

Group model building is used to involve stakeholders and capture knowledge, increase the chances of implementation of model results, and enhance the stakeholder/client learning processes (Vennix 1999). In environmental science, group model building has been used to involve more than one expert to increase the validity and robustness of a model (Costanza *et al.* 1990). A recent development has been to use group model building to involve stakeholders in developing environmental management policy (for example Stave 2002, Stave 2003, and Wolfenden 1999).

Stakeholders may participate in group model building to different degrees. Stave (2003) identifies a spectrum of participation when involving stakeholders in model building for environmental management. At the least participatory level, a completed model may be used to demonstrate the effects of alternative policies to stakeholders. A more participatory approach would allow stakeholders to suggest scenarios to be tested. At the most participatory level stakeholders can help develop the simulation model that represents system structure.

The group model building process has been described as more of an art than a science (Anderson *et al.* 1997). Methods used to build group models usually involve conferences (for example Anderson and Richardson 1997) or workshops (for example Maani 2000, Wolfenden 1999). Techniques used within these group model building forums are varied and rarely well documented (Anderson and Richardson 1997). The variety of techniques used in group model building relate to its many purposes and levels of participation. Some cases emphasise the model outcome, for example learning from the insights gained by playing with the model. Others emphasise the process, for example consensus-building and team learning through the development of conceptual models.

The development of a simulation model *per se* is not required where more importance is placed on the process. Bellamy and MacLeod (1999) found that the effectiveness of participative model building is as much an outcome of the development and implementation of the process as the potential usefulness of the decision support system product itself. Further, it has been argued that although quantification of conceptual models may add to understanding of an issue, they may also be dangerously misleading (Wolstenholme 1992, 1999, Coyle 2000, Maani 2000). Flexibility needs to be a recognised component of the methodology.

System Dynamics modelling has been used to conceptualise the complexities of water resources management and development of water policy (for example Abbott and Stanley 1999, Ford 1996, Teegavarapu and Simonovic 2000). Wolfenden (1999) and Stave (2002, 2003) have used group model building to facilitate greater public participation in water planning and decision making. This paper describes two uses for group model building:

1. To improve a prototype System Dynamics model; and
2. To elicit issues are of critical importance stakeholders and relate these issues to the existing decision making framework.

To demonstrate the potential of System Dynamics modelling for improved stakeholder involvement in water management decision making, a case study using the development of the Draft Water Sharing Plan for Coopers Creek, NSW, was undertaken. The Northern Rivers Water Management Committee (the Committee) is responsible for developing Water Sharing Plans for a range of high conservation value catchments in the Northern Rivers region of northern NSW. The Committee was formed in 2000 and has twenty-four members representing seven non-government organisations, three local government agencies, six state government agencies and the Northern Rivers Catchment Management Board (stakeholders). The monthly meetings of the Committee from June 2000 to December 2001 form the basis of this research.

After attending a number of meetings it became apparent that not all of the decision-support information being produced for Committee members (mostly derived from the responsible department's Integrated Quantitative Qualitative Modelling (IQQM)) was useful or easily relatable to the expertise of committee members, and requested information was difficult to extract from the relatively inflexible models being used by the Department responsible for the process. As a result, much time was spent trying to incorporate issues of concern to stakeholders into the decision making process. A real-time model at the property scale was required so that the link between stakeholders and the decision support information they were receiving was more efficient and relevant. It was thought that System Dynamics modelling had the potential to provide a flexible and real-time simulation where the existing models could not.

Methods

Research Framework

The evaluation of the use of Systems Dynamics modelling by the Committee was structured around an Action Research cycle (Figure 1). This cycle began by developing key relationships with stakeholders and researching the management system. A prototype simulator was developed to assist stakeholders to visualise the existing understanding of the data given, and introduce them to the System Dynamics approach. The models described in this paper were built using *iThink* software, a third generation computer language. The next stage in the Action Research Cycle was the group model building workshop where:

1. the prototype model was presented to Committee members;
2. Options were discussed for the group model building project and deliberated upon. This ensured the group owned the process and the model they were building was their own;

3. Issues for each stakeholder were identified;
4. Relationships between the issues were identified and a conceptual model developed; and
5. The group model building workshop concluded with an evaluation of the process.

In the final stage the work was reflected upon (for example in the reflection embodied in this paper), allowing the system to be revised.

Figure 1: Action Research Cycle

Results

Developing key relationships and system understanding

The author was a member of the Committee and regularly attended meetings. Good working relationships with Committee members were thus established before conducting the exercise. Further, as a stakeholder in the decision making process, the researcher (den Exter) had a good understanding of the water management decision making system and the information available. The development of a prototype model did not take as long as it might have had the author not been so involved.

The Water Management Simulator Prototype

To ensure transparency, comprehension and validity, the prototype Water Management Simulator (WATERSIM) was developed using data that had already been given to committee members by the NSW Department of Land and Water Conservation (now the NSW Department of Infrastructure Planning and Natural Resources) and understanding of the processes and linkages built up by attendance at the committee meetings. No new parameters or data were introduced until after the group model building workshop.

The major sectors of WATERSIM are flow, maximum extractable water, flow balance, the 'cease to pump' and water sharing rules (Figure 2). Flow balance is influenced by the amount of flow entering the system, the 'cease to pump' limit, and the allowable maximum amount of extractable water. These factors are determined by the flow rules. The flow balance has a feedback relationship with the allowable maximum amount of extractable water. Flow in this model is user defined and is actual, or simulated where there are data gaps, daily flow for a wet, dry or average year. The data are derived from the NSW Department of Land and Water Conservation (DLWC)'s Integrated Quantitative Qualitative Modelling (IQQM) data, which were the information base for decision-making by the Committee. The flow balance is a balance between actual flow and water extracted. The 'cease to pump' is a trigger level set by the Committee at which flows are considered sufficiently low that pumping must cease. Prior to the development of the water sharing plans the 'cease to pump' trigger was visual flow.

Figure 2: Relationships in the prototype Water Management Simulator (WATERSIM)

The main interface that the user sees in WATERSIM is the control panel (Figure 3). It allows the user to choose flow data for a particular year, and define water-sharing rules. Results of the user-defined scenarios are displayed on the graph pad. Variables displayed are flow in (actual flow data (mL/day) selected by the user), environmental flow (flow remaining after extraction in mL/day), the amount of flow able to be extracted (mL/day) and the cease to pump (mL/day) over one year.

Two indices are also included on the control panel - the irrigation index and the environmental flow index. The irrigation index was programmed to flash red if the amount of flow able to be extracted was less than the predicted peak daily demand (determined from figures provided by the NSW Department of Agriculture to the Committee). The environmental flow index was programmed to flash red when the environmental flow levels fell below the known requirements of Eastern Freshwater Cod (a listed threatened species) for fish passage (e.g. 15ML/day).

Figure 3: WATERSIM control panel. The control panel allows the user to experiment with daily flow data for typical wet, dry or average years, different cease to pump levels ranging from 17mL to 200mL at the end of the system gauge and different water rules (bulk access regimes) for the A, B and C flow classes. The results of each run are displayed on the graph in terms of the daily flow in (determined by the flow data selected), environmental flow (flow left after extraction), extraction (determined by the water rules) and the cease to pump (CTP). The irrigation index is an indicator of when demand is not satisfied (e.g. it flashes red when the peak daily demand is not met). The environmental flow index is an indicator of when environmental flow requirements are not met, for instance in terms of requirements for Eastern Freshwater Cod migration and breeding.

Group Model Building Workshop

The System Dynamics group model building workshop was conducted on the 23rd August 2002. Between the twelve workshop participants all member organisations of the Northern Rivers Water Management Committee were represented at the workshop. Results from the group model building process are summarised below.

1. Presentation of prototype model

WATERSIM was presented to the group by demonstration of the model and its operation. Inputs to the WATERSIM model were outputs from NSW DLWC hydrological and irrigation modelling, and these and the representativeness of existing committee understanding were the focus of discussion. Workshop participants had a good understanding of the assumptions behind the model, and they all had hard copy tables and graphs of the data to refer to at the workshop.

2. Deciding the model focus

Four options for model-building were generated from areas of concern previously identified by the stakeholders. These included further development of the prototype, but also included other options so that the

facilitator did not dominate the direction of proceedings, but to allow stakeholders to govern the process and hence have greater ownership of and commitment to it. The four options presented were to:

1. continue to examine the water management simulator;
2. develop an issues-based model to examine inter-relationships between stakeholder issues;
3. develop a dairy-farm model to examine the effects of the water-sharing plan on an average farm; or
4. develop a model for the Eastern Freshwater Cod to be used as an environmental indicator.

After some discussion the dairy-farmer model option was chosen. Reasons for choosing the dairy-farm option included participant concern about the effect of the Committee’s recommendations on dairy farmers in the Coopers Creek sub-catchment and the knowledge that the Committee would have little input into the next stage of planning and development of the implementation plan. Developing their own model of dairy farm effects was seen by stakeholders as one avenue in which issues outside the ‘role’ or statutory obligations of the Committee could be examined with relation to the decisions that the Committee had the power to make.

3. Issue identification

Results of the brainstorming process highlighted issues of concern to members of the Committee (Table 1). The group had to decide at this point on the model boundaries. Initially water managed was the main focus but the focus shifted to the modelling the milk production system, the understanding of which was considered critical at a property-scale when properly considering water management options and which had not been considered in the wider process to date (Figure 4). All issues classified as endogenous and exogenous were included in the model developed by the Committee. Factors in the outer ring, although recognised as important effectors of the milk production system, were excluded from the conceptual model as uncontrollable variables.

Table 1: Dairy farmer issues identified by modelling workshop group

Pumping hours	Rostering	Benefits
Daily access	Resource security	Profit
Cut-out time	Active versus inactive licences	Production system
Number of paddocks under irrigation	Costs – animal health, feed, fertiliser, mgt	Infrastructure alternatives
Demand for milk	Water sharing	Management and labour
Seasonality	Water users group	Feed price
	Water trading	NORCO benefit
	Demand for water	Calving relationship

Figure 4: Milk Production System Model boundaries and issues categorisation.

4. Development of Conceptual Model

The initial model of milk production developed by the group contained all the elements considered important by each stakeholder and illustrated the connections between them. Ideas flowed freely from the floor and were recorded on butcher's paper before conversion into the *iThink* System Dynamics modelling software. Limitations were evident at this stage as the butcher's paper was too small for all participants to clearly see what was being recorded and additional facilitation would have enabled faster recording and more discussion as elements were suggested for inclusion. The Milk Production System model (Figure 5) shows how stakeholders perceive links between water management decision-making and the profitability of a dairy enterprise, thus making the consequence of their decisions more real for them. It also established the role and importance of decisions by the water user group in the determination of daily access to water.

Figure 5: The Milk Production System conceptual model developed by stakeholders at the workshop.

5. Evaluation

Participants were asked to evaluate their experience at the end of the group model building workshop by anonymously responding to four questions:

- (1) What was the best/most positive aspect of the exercise?
- (2) What would you like to have seen done differently?
- (3) How do you think this type of approach could assist the Northern Rivers Water Management Committee?
- (4) Any further comments?

Participant responses to these questions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Responses to evaluation questions

<i>Question 1: What was the best/most positive aspect of the exercise?</i>	∞ Highlighted problems of water sharing.
	∞ Highlighted processes, linkages and outcomes.
	∞ Holistic approach.
	∞ Use of qualitative factors.
	∞ Explored different understandings.
	∞ Brought together different ideas and interpretations.
	∞ Involved everyone/group participation.
	∞ Helped understand modelling process and assumptions.
<i>Question 2: What would you like to have seen done differently?</i>	∞ Visual aspect of the exercise.
	∞ Start simpler before moving to more complex models.
	∞ Develop model purpose/aim more carefully/specifically.
	∞ More in depth explanation.
<i>Question 3: How do you think this type of approach could assist the Committee?</i>	∞ Resources: more time, better location, bigger butchers paper, co-facilitator.
	∞ Useful for communication.
	∞ Could be useful for decision support but who will do it?
	∞ Developing a holistic picture where social, economic and environmental issues are all taken into account.
	∞ Looking at trade-offs.
	∞ Helping to see interactive and connective nature of issues.
	∞ Small group work productive.
	∞ Assists thought processes.
<i>Comments</i>	∞ Assists in understanding the outcomes of decisions.
	∞ Helpful in understanding the complexities of a water plan.
	∞ A useful session
	∞ Willing to do more
	∞ Relevant to whole committee
	∞ What kind of commitment is required to get a decision support system developed.

Revision of system understanding and prototype model

The original water management simulator (WATERSIM) was revised using the understanding developed in the Milk Production System (MPS) model (Figure 5). In this second version of the water management simulator (Figure 6) a daily access sector was added to the prototype (Figure 2) based on the material developed for the MPS model. The importance of extractable water to the calculation of daily access was defined as the integration point for all the inputs, the 'cease to pump' options feeding into the flow balance calculation before being incorporated into the determination of the amount of water extractable. This allowed for farm-scale analysis of the implications of the different decision options for the 'cease to pump' limit at a daily access level and produced more realistic, relevant, and sensitive results than the initial prototype. With further development, the model could be used to assist water user groups negotiate and trade water shares, thus reducing negative impacts arising from the Water Sharing Plans.

Figure 6: Relationships between model sectors in the revised WATERSIM model where the allowable maximum extractable water now also influences daily access to water.

Discussion

The prototype model (WATERSIM) provided a good introduction to System Dynamics modelling for Committee members as it illustrated its potential for real-time simulation. As workshop participants had a good understanding of the assumptions behind the data, explaining the parameters and assumptions of the WATERSIM model was much easier than if new parameters had been used. Using parameters that participants were already familiar with also assisted in explaining the language of System Dynamics. As indicated from the evaluation responses (Table 2), more time was needed to go into the detail of the model and the System Dynamics method if participants were to understand the structure and behaviour of the model and use it more fully.

The conceptual model developed by stakeholders (Figure 5) demonstrates that developing useful model 'products' is feasible using group model building in a very short time with limited resources. The workshop produced a conceptual model useful in its own right for stakeholder communication and understanding. The model developed by stakeholders was easily incorporated into the prototype model of the water management decision making system (WATERSIM) providing information at the property scale.

At the start of the workshop a number of participants expressed a lack of confidence in their ability to build models despite being familiar with modelling as a decision support tool. These participants quickly overcame their fears to enthusiastically participate in and learn from the exercise. As Stave (2003) found, stakeholders participating in group model building did not need to know anything about systems modelling to gain system insights.

Participant responses to the evaluation questions were encouraging. Participants found that the process was inclusive and that it enabled the exploration of different understandings. Perhaps most importantly, participants found that they developed a holistic view of the water management system. Participants also

commented that the workshop was useful in facilitating a better understanding of the model development process.

Constructive criticism of the workshop predominantly related to resources, for example lack of time, the need for more in-depth explanations, and the need for an additional facilitator. A number of comments related to the usefulness of the approach, but questioned whether it would be adopted in the longer-term as it would need commitment and funding. These 'resource factors' are controllable and could be overcome if the benefits are seen to outweigh the costs of the exercise.

Conclusion

To understand and manage environmental systems requires communication and learning between stakeholders and an adaptive approach to decision-making and decision support. This case study demonstrates the potential of System Dynamics group model building for improving stakeholder involvement in environmental management decision making. System Dynamics group model building is a useful tool for developing and improving models that integrate existing information with stakeholder issues and knowledge. Further, the models produced enabled real-time simulation at a scale relevant to the users.

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References

- Abbott, M.D. and Stanley, R.S. (1999). Modeling Groundwater Recharge and Flow in an Upland Fractured Bedrock Aquifer. *System Dynamics Review* 15(2), 163-184.
- Anderson, D.F., Richardson, G.P. and Vennix, J.A.M. (1997). Group Model Building: Adding More Science to the Craft. *System Dynamics Review* 13(2), 187-201.
- Anderson, D.F. and Richardson, G.P. (1997). Scripts for Group Model Building. *Systems Dynamics Review* 13(2), 107-129.
- Bellamy, J. and MacLeod, N. (1999). Evaluating the Effectiveness of Information Technology for Complex Multiple Objective Decision-making Contexts: Process Tool or Product Success. MODSS'99 - 2nd International Conference on Multiple Objective Decision Support Systems for Land, Water and Environmental Management, Sheraton Hotel, Brisbane (State of Queensland, Department of Natural Resources).
- Costanza, R., Sklar, F.H. and White, M.L. (1990). Modeling Coastal Landscape Dynamics. *BioScience* 40(2), 91-107.
- Coyle, G. (2000). Qualitative and Quantitative Modelling in System Dynamics: Some Research Questions. *System Dynamics Review* 16(3), 25-244.
- Cullen, P. (2000). Water Reforms, Science and Ecological Outcomes in Australia. International Water Resources Association 10th World Water Congress, Melbourne (International Water Resources Association).
- den Exter, K. (2003 (subm)). Integrating Environmental Science and Management: The Role of System Dynamics Modelling. Phd Thesis. (School of Resource Science and Management. Southern Cross University, Lismore).
- Doyle, J.K. (1997). The Cognitive Psychology of Systems Thinking. *System Dynamics Review* 13(3), 253-265.
- Forrester, J.W. (1960). The Impact of Feedback Control Concepts on the Management Sciences. In 'Collected Papers of J.W. Forrester'. pp 45-60 (Wright Allen Press Cambridge, MA).
- Lane, D.C. and Oliva, R. (1998). The Greater Whole: Towards a Synthesis of System Dynamics and Soft Systems Methodology. *European Journal of Operational Research* 107, 214-235.
- Maani, K. (2000). Group Model Building for Consensus Building and Team Learning - A Case Study. Sustainability in the Third Millennium - 18th International Conference of the System Dynamics Society, Bergen, Norway. (The System Dynamics Society).
- Meadows, D.H. (1989). System Dynamics Meets the Press. *System Dynamics Review* 5(1), 68-80.

- Kerin, J.C. (2000). Involving the Community in Water Management. International Water Resources Association 10th World Water Congress. (International Water Resources Association Melbourne).
- Stave, K.A. (2002). Using System Dynamics to Improve Public Participation in Environmental Decisions. *System Dynamics Review* 18(2), 139-167.
- Stave, K.A. (2003). A System Dynamics Model to Facilitate Public Understanding of Water Management Options in Las Vegas, Nevada. *Journal of Environmental Management* 67, 303-313.
- Teegavarapu, R.S.V. and Simonovic, S.P. (2000). System Dynamics Simulation Model for the Operation of Multiple Reservoirs. International Water Resources Association 10th World Water Congress. (IWRA Melbourne).
- Weil, H.B. (1980). The Evolution of an Approach for Achieving Implemented Results from System Dynamics Projects. In 'Elements of the System Dynamics Method' (Ed J. Randers) pp. 271-291. (MIT Press Cambridge, Massachusetts).
- Vennix, J.A.M. (1999). Group Model-building: Tackling Messy Problems. *System Dynamics Review* 15(4), 379-401.
- Wolfenden, J. (1999). A Transdisciplinary Approach to Integrated Resource Management: A Pragmatic Application of Ecological Economics. PhD Thesis. (Centre for Water Policy Research, University of New England Armidale).
- Wolstenholme, E.F. (1990). 'System Enquiry - A System Dynamics Approach'. (John Wiley and Sons Chichester).
- Wolstenholme, E.F. (1999). Qualitative versus Quantitative Modelling: The Evolving Balance. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* 50, 422-428.